

IMPACT STRENGTH OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic tensile tests, foreign object impact tests and low velocity flexural tests were performed on unidirectional boron/aluminum composites and laminated plates in order to clarify impact behavior of metal matrix composites. Strain rate sensitivity in tensile strength, foreign object damage and capability to absorb impact energy were investigated. As a result of these impact tests, the impact behavior of metal matrix composites became more apparent.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced metal matrix composites are expected to be superior to fiber reinforced plastics in impact strength due to the fact that the matrix is metal. But little reports are published for the impact behavior of metal matrix composites. So if metal matrix composites are to be applied for use in practical structures like jet engine components, it will be necessary to examine the impact strength of metal matrix composites experimentally and to determine the allowable limit theoretically.

In the present paper, in order to clarify the impact behavior of metal matrix composites, dynamic tensile tests, foreign object impact tests and low velocity flexural tests were performed on unidirectional boron/aluminum composites and laminated plates. Strain rate sensitivity in tensile strength was investigated and foreign object impact damage was observed. The capability to absorb impact energy was also examined.

MATERIAL

The materials used in this study are boron/aluminum-6061 composite plates fabricated by the hot press method. The composite plate was 150mm square and the volume fraction of the fiber was 0.38. The specimen geometry and size were different for three types of specimens.

DYNAMIC TENSILE TESTS OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES¹

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A conventional testing machine was used for the static tensile tests, whereas a rotating disc type machine was used for the dynamic tensile tests. The latter machine employs a block-to-bar method² and schematic drawing of the machine is shown in Fig. 1. One-dimensional stress wave propagation theory is used to obtain dynamic tensile stress and strain in the specimen. The dynamic tensile stress and strain can be expressed by

$$\sigma(t) = \frac{S_o}{S} \cdot E_o \cdot \varepsilon_g \left(t + \frac{a}{c} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{1}{\ell} \int_0^t \left\{ V(t) - C \varepsilon_g \left(t + \frac{a}{c} \right) \right\} dt \quad (2)$$

where ε_g is measured by semiconductor gages located at a distance 'a' from the end of the output bar (Fig. 1), ℓ and S are the length and the cross sectional area of the specimen, S_o , E_o and c are the cross sectional area, Young's modulus and the longitudinal elastic wave velocity of the output bar, and $V(t)$ is the velocity of the impact block. The test specimens for the static and dynamic tensile tests are shown in Figures 2 and 3. Due

Fig. 1 Schematic drawing of the dynamic tensile testing machine

Specimen	t
0°	0.8
45°	3.2
90°	3.2
(0°/90°) _s	0.8

Fig. 2 Specimen for static tensile tests

Specimen	L	B	t
0°	138	3.5	0.8
45°	108	3.2	3.2
90°	58	3.2	3.2
(0°/90°) _s	88	4.5	0.8

Fig. 3 Specimen for dynamic tensile tests

Table 1 Effect of strain rate on tensile strength

Specimen	Static		Dynamic		$\frac{\sigma_d}{\sigma_s}$
	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ (1/s)	Tensile strength σ_s (MPa)	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ (1/s)	Tensile strength σ_d (MPa)	
0°	833×10^{-5}	1170	1.67×10^3	1200	1.02
45°	833×10^{-4}	162	1.55×10^3	192	1.18
90°	833×10^{-5}	148	1.48×10^3	202	1.36
(0°/90°) _s	833×10^{-5}	554	1.74×10^3	554	1.00
Aluminum alloy 6061-0	1.04×10^{-3}	136	1.82×10^3	168	1.24

1 MPa = 0.102 kgf/mm²

Fig. 4 Stress-strain curves for static and dynamic tensile tests

to the difficulty of processing, adhesive type specimens were used for the dynamic tensile tests. Unidirectional composites of 0° , 45° and 90° and $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminated plates were used for the tests.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Stress-strain curves for the unidirectional 0° , 90° and $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminated specimens obtained from the static and dynamic tensile tests are shown in Fig. 4. In Fig. 4, the dotted and solid lines represent static and dynamic testing results, respectively. The tensile strength of the composites obtained by the tests is summarized in Table 1. The results for aluminum alloy 6061-O are also shown. The 45° and the 90° specimens, where the tensile strength is expected to depend on the matrix, indicate the strain rate sensitivity, since the aluminum alloy shows an increase in tensile strength with increasing strain rate. On the other hand, the tensile strength of the 0° and $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminated specimens shows no strain rate sensitivity. Consequently, the tensile strength of boron fibers is estimated to be independent of the strain rate.

FOREIGN OBJECT IMPACT TESTS OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A powder gun was used to accelerate steel projectiles for the foreign object impact tests and schematic drawing of the machine is shown in Fig. 5. Specimen dimension is 150 mm square, where test area is 100 mm square. Stacking sequences are unidirectional, $((0^\circ/90^\circ)_4/0^\circ)$ and $(0^\circ_3/90^\circ_3/0^\circ_3)$ with nominal thickness of 2 mm, and unidirectional, $((0^\circ/90^\circ)_7/0^\circ)$ and $((0^\circ_3/90^\circ_3)_2/0^\circ_3)$ with nominal thickness of 3.2 mm. All four sides of the specimen are fixed and the nominal diameter of the projectile is 5 mm. A high-speed camera was used to measure the velocity of the projectile.

Fig. 5 Schematic drawing of the the foreign object impact machine

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Impact damage of unidirectional composites is shown in Fig. 6. The observed damage is classified as small dimple, surface crack, plug growth and perforation. Relation between the failure mode and the impact velocity is expressed as follows.

When the impact velocity of the projectile is low, a small dimple appeared on the front surface of the specimen. As the projectile is gradually accelerated, surface crack occurred on the rear surface of the specimen. The specimen is subjected to severe damage at faster impact velocity and rectangular plug appeared. After the impact velocity of the projectile is beyond the threshold velocity, the projectile perforates into specimen. Similar failure modes to unidirectional composites are observed for laminated plates. Failure modes are not affected by the stacking sequence and thickness of the specimens. Sectional photographs of impacted specimens are shown in Fig. 7. When the impact velocity is slightly below the threshold velocity, small delamination is observed in laminated plates, but this delamination is not apparent when compared with that of the fiber reinforced plastics. Residual deformation of the specimen is small and restricted to the vicinity of the impacted area. From the conservation of energy and the conservation of momentum, threshold velocity to cause perforation damage is calculated by

Fig. 6 Impact damage of unidirectional composites

Fig. 7 Sectional photographs of impacted specimens

$$V_{xn} = \left[V^2 - \left(\frac{M_p + M_{sn}}{M_p} \right)^2 V_r^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

where M_p is the mass of the projectile, M_{sn} is the mass of the plug, and V and V_r are the impact velocity and the residual velocity of the projectile respectively. In Eq. 3, it is assumed that the plug grows after the projectile penetrates into specimen and the velocity of the plug after perforation is the same as the one of the projectile. Impact energies calculated from the threshold velocity is shown in Fig. 8. Impact energies to cause perforation damage have no distinct difference between the unidirectional composites and the laminated plates. This result is attributed to the fact that the failure modes of unidirectional composites and laminated plates are almost same and no other failure mode appears.

Fig. 8 Impact energies to cause perforation damage

LOW VELOCITY FLEXURAL TESTS OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

An instrumented pendulum type impact machine was used for the low velocity flexural tests and schematic drawing of the machine is shown in Fig. 9. Mass of the pendulum is 7 kg and maximum impact velocity is 3.7 m/s. Specimen dimension is 15 mm by 150 mm, where span length is 60 mm. Both sides of the specimen are fixed. Stacking sequences are 0° , 90° , $((0^\circ/90^\circ)_4/0^\circ)$ and $(\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ with nominal thickness of 2 mm and 0° , 90° , $((0^\circ/90^\circ)_9/0^\circ)$ and $(\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)_{2s}$ with nominal thickness of 4 mm. Traces of load-time were measured by semiconductor gages attached on the top of the pendulum and absorbed energies were calculated from these traces.

Fig. 9 Schematic drawing of the low velocity flexural machine

Fig. 10 Absorbed energies per unit sectional thickness

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Incident impact energy was varied by changing the angle of the pendulum and absorbed energy was calculated for the failed specimen. Absorbed energies per unit sectional thickness are shown in Fig. 10. These values depend on the type of specimen and independent of the incident impact energies. Absorbed energies of the 0° specimens, cross-ply laminated specimens and pseudo-isotropic laminated specimens are less than that of 90° specimens. This will be caused by the difference of the failure modes, where 0° specimens and laminated plates are brittle and considerable plastic deformation occurs for 90° specimens.

CONCLUSION

Dynamic tensile tests, foreign object impact tests and low velocity flexural tests were performed on unidirectional boron/aluminum composites and laminated plates. The following conclusions were obtained:

- 1) The tensile strength of the 45° and 90° specimens is strain rate sensitive but 0° and (0°/90°) laminated specimens are immune to strain rate.
- 2) Impact energies to cause perforation damage have no distinct difference between unidirectional composites and laminated plates.
- 3) Absorbed energies of the 0° specimens, cross-ply laminated specimens and pseudo-isotropic laminated specimens are less than that of 90° specimens.
- 4) These experimental results suggest that impact strength of boron/aluminum composites are inferior to that of aluminum alloys.

As a result of these impact tests, the impact behavior of metal matrix composites became more apparent.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was performed under the management of the Research and Development Institute of Metals and Composites for Future Industries sponsored by the Agency of Industrial Science and Technology, MITI.

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